

BOOK REVIEW**Daniela Koleva**

"Medical Anthropology", Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Studies with Ethnographic Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
 [koleva@phls.uni-sofia.bg]

What is 'Soviet' about Soviet Ageing?¹

Abstract: *This book explores ageing in the Soviet Union from different perspectives: in the context of scientific, educational, and media discourses, in terms of social care and urbanism, and from gender and generational standpoints. In addition, Soviet ageing is innovatively placed in a broader context. The volume is the result of a collaborative and interdisciplinary effort of researchers with deep and long-standing interest in Soviet history, as well as researchers who reside in the countries of the former Soviet Union.*

Keywords: *Soviet Union; ageing; gerontology.*

Susan Grant and Isaac McKean Scarborough (eds.) **Geriatrics and Ageing in the Soviet Union: Medical, Political and Social Contexts.** London – New York – Oxford – New Delhi – Sydney: Bloomsbury Academic, 2023, 256 p.

I am writing to recommend this book to researchers, students and anyone else interested in the history of medicine, medical anthropology, the social history of the Soviet Union, or ageing studies more broadly. The volume offers a variety of perspectives on ageing: in the context of scientific, educational, and media discourses, in terms of social care and urbanism, as

¹ This text is part of my work on the project 'Taming the European Leviathan: Postwar Medicine and the Common Good' supported by the European Research Council (grant agreement No. 854503).

well as from gender and generational standpoints.

The first section focuses on the scientific perspective. It opens with an overview of the development of Soviet gerontology written by two of its leading figures: Vladislav Bezrukov, the long-serving Director of the Institute of Gerontology in Kyiv, which was the centre of Soviet gerontology, and Yurii Duplenko, one of the Institute's first employees, who dedicated his entire career to its growth. The authors discuss the ideas on the biological mechanisms of ageing advanced by the pioneers of Soviet gerontology, highlighting the continuity in its development, which lead to its consolidation from the 1930s on and to its institutionalisation with the founding of the Institute in 1958. They outline the research areas in which the Institute excelled and gained international recognition, as evidenced by its hosting of the 9th Congress of the International Association of Gerontology in 1972.

While the first chapter deals with 'hard science,' the next two chapters focus on what might be called 'visionary science' or rather, visionary belief in science as a means to 'conquer' nature, including human nature – the natural processes of ageing and dying. Maria Tutorskaya discusses the intertwining of the Bolshevik revolution with the revolutionary changes in science, which increased its public visibility: the experimental turn in life sciences and their expansion in scale. In particular, the rise of experimental endocrinology generated a 'secular mythology' (p. 47) of sorts, around the idea of human rejuvenation and longevity, tied to the revolutionary project of reorganising society. In the following chapter, Anna Ozhiganova delves into another stream of 'visionary' science: Ilya Arshavsky's theory of the positive influence of stress factors (such as cold) at the early stages of ontogenesis. Arshavsky claimed that cold exposure and physical exertion would 'wind up the clock of life' (p. 65) and have beneficial effects later in life. This theory inspired not only (para-)scientific experiments (most notably Igor Charkovsky's 'aquaculture') but also parental attitudes. The 'visionary physiology' gained popularity in the 1980s in the context of the late Soviet 'alternative science', which obviously responded to the needs and anxieties of the time.

The second section addresses issues of care and support for older people. Alexandra Brokman offers a case study of post-WWII psychiatric care, emphasizing the tendency of medical institutions to see older people as 'bodies' rather than persons, prioritising their bodily needs. Her account of the 'management of bodies' shows a striking parallel with Agamben's concept of 'bare life' in concentration camps: a state of de-

humanization where the person is reduced to mere existence between life and death.

In contrast to the challenge that elderly, disabled and psychiatric patients presented to the Soviet project by failing to fit into the narrative of progressive change, the next two chapters focus on efforts to accommodate the needs of elderly people in an attempt to 'humanize' housing and urban environments. In her meticulously researched chapter, Susan Grant explores the design of care homes. Work being the highest value in Soviet society, care homes were initially intended to enable an active life for their residents. However, the residents' physical condition often called for a medical environment, rather than one akin to a home. The author views the need to balance care and independent living more as an intellectual challenge to be solved by architects and designers, rather than a practical one for local administrations and social services. In the same vein, Botakoz Kassymbekova discusses urbanists' visions of built environments that would be friendly to older people. She reveals the dilemma of accommodating older people's desire for independent living versus their need to be close to their adult children. The author draws on sociological surveys from the 1970s and 1980s to reveal how the vision of 'good ageing' was formed and how it guided proposals for improving the situation of older people in cities. However, it remains unclear if any of these proposals was implemented.

The third section deals with representations and discourses of ageing and old age. In her fascinating chapter, Danielle Leavitt-Quist captures the controversies surrounding the 'modern babushka' who diverged from the traditional grandmother roles. The issue was not limited to the changing life style of a cohort of (mostly) educated urban women but also touched upon more fundamental values such as Soviet morality, solidarity, duty, and the hierarchies of socially useful work: care work versus paid work. The problem goes beyond gender stereotypes to the ambivalent nature of communist emancipation, which prescribed full-time employment for women without challenging traditional gender roles. As a result, retired women were vital to the everyday functioning of Soviet society (as well as Bulgarian, Romanian, etc.). By re-framing the issue as a moral one, rather than a systemic one, public debates often suggested a return of older women to traditional gender roles thus pitting generations against each other.

The theme of generation is central in Alissa Klots' and Maria Romashova's chapter on how late Soviet memory politics contributed to the self-perception of retired women who volunteered to collect and organize

material for local archives. The captivating case they analyze demonstrates how memory work together with one's elders and peers led to older women-activists' reimagining themselves as the pioneer generation that built socialism. In this way, they inserted themselves into the official Soviet historical narrative and constructed a vindicated self-identity vis-à-vis younger generations.

Finally, Katarzyna Jarosz compares several medical museums in different post-Soviet countries, focusing on the representations of the life cycle in order to distill a narrative 'not only on individuals' Soviet ontogenesis, but the ontogenesis of the Soviet medical system' (p. 167). Her striking finding is that old age and death as phases of the life cycle are conspicuously absent from all surveyed museums. Insofar as death is portrayed, it is always the heroic death of soldiers defending the motherland, bearing a completely different message than one might expect in a museum of medicine.

The last section of the volume seems to diverge from its announced focus on the Soviet Union by introducing other country cases: Ewelina Szpak's chapter on the plight of older people in People's Poland, where old age was excluded from the socialist project and 'was tabooed as a social problem' (p. 192), is juxtaposed with an account of the development of gerontology and the attitudes towards older people in post-WWII UK, where non-state actors, such as the Nuffield Foundation, were the ones to take the lead. While well researched and compellingly argued, these chapters leave some doubt about the need for such contextualization. It might have been better in terms of coherence, if (an)other country case(s) from the Soviet bloc were brought in for comparison. However, the editors seem committed to a global perspective, concluding the volume with an epilogue penned by James Chappel and Isaac Scarborough that ambitiously places socialist (not only Soviet) ageing in a global context. The authors indeed successfully pull together the 'loose ends' of the individual chapters and defend their approach by identifying four major thematic fields in ageing studies: science, rural ageing, gender and race/ethnicity/empire. (The last theme's relevance to ageing in the Soviet world, as the authors admit, remains unclear.) To these, I would add the crosscutting theme of representation, which draws attention to the cultural lens through which ageing is viewed – a dimension present in all chapters.²

² For recent work exploring representations of ageing, see the chapters on 'literary gerontology' in Dagmar Gramshammer-Hohl and Oana Hergenröther (2021).

My reservations are, first, that the global perspective actually becomes a backdrop for US-USSR parallels, and second, that some of these parallels seem rather bold. For example, while there were indeed parallels and cross-fertilisations in the field of gerontology, as Scarborough proves in his excellent in-depth study (Scarborough 2022), this was the case in the second half of the 20th century. The earlier period of ideologically informed 'visionary science' falls out of the picture, although it is thematised in some chapters. Tellingly, what was to become the Institute of Gerontology in Kyiv, was initially conceived as an 'Institute for the Study of Longevity' (Ibid.: 1251), in tune with earlier utopian visions. Moreover, the state's 'flattening' of citizens into standardized categories was often based on ideological principles, as Szpak shows in relation to private farmers in Poland.³ Also, while Soviet and American older women did face similar challenges, a 'women's movement that was urging women towards equal standing' (p. 235) existed only in the latter case, while in the former, such a movement was theoretically impossible due to the claim that full emancipation was already achieved (and practically impossible, because of state control).

Despite these reservations, I do recommend this book - not only because the individual chapters are well-conceived, well-researched, and written by top scholars in their fields, many of whom reside in the region of the former Soviet Union, but also because the volume opens up new directions for research, reflection and discussion.

Bibliography:

Gramshammer-Hohl, D. and O. Hergenröther (eds.) (2021) *Foreign Countries of Old Age: East and Southeast European Perspectives on Aging*. Aging Studies, vol. 19. Bielefeld: Transcript Verlag.

Scarborough, I. McK. (2022) A New Science for an Old(er) Population: Soviet Gerontology and Geriatrics in International Comparative Perspective. *Social History of Medicine*, 35(4), 1247-1266.

Koleva, D. (forthcoming) How Can Care Produce Inequality? The privileges of the "active fighters against fascism and capitalism" in communist Bulgaria. *Südost-Forschungen*.

³ For another case of ideologisation of age see Daniela Koleva (forthcoming).